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Constructing an interlaced catalytic surface via fluorine-doped bimetallic oxides for oxygen electrode processes in Li–O₂ batteries

Zongqiang Sun[#], Xiaodong Lin[#], Chutao Wang[#], Yanyan Tan, Wenjie Dou, Ajuan Hu, Jiaqing Cui, Jingmin Fan, Ruming Yuan, Mingsen Zheng and Quanfeng Dong**

Z. Sun, X. Lin, C. Wang, Y. Tan, W. Dou, A. Hu, J. Cui, J. Fan, R. Yuan, M. Zheng, Q. Dong

State Key Laboratory of Physical Chemistry of Solid Surfaces, Collaborative Innovation Center of Chemistry for Energy Materials (i-ChEM), Engineering Research Centre of Electrochemical Technologies of Ministry of Education, Department of Chemistry, College of Chemistry and Chemical Engineering, Xiamen University, 361005, Xiamen, China.

X. Lin

Institute of Condensed Matter and Nanosciences, Université Catholique de Louvain, Louvain-la-Neuve B-1348, Belgium.

M. Zheng, Q. Dong

Innovation Laboratory for Sciences and Technologies of Energy Materials of Fujian Province (IKKEM), Xiamen, 361005, China.

Email of the corresponding author: mszheng@xmu.edu.cn; qfdong@xmu.edu.cn

[#]These authors contributed equally to this work.

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Abstract

Lithium–oxygen (Li–O₂) batteries, renowned for their exceptionally high theoretical energy density, have garnered significant interest as a prime candidate for future electric device development. However, practical testing often yields unsatisfactory capacity due to the tendency of their solid-phase discharge products to cover active sites on the electrode surface. Optimizing the growth mechanism of these solid-phase products and addressing the storage issue to narrow the gap between actual and theoretical capacities stands as the core challenge in Li–O₂ battery development. Here, a fluorine-doped bimetallic cobalt-nickel oxide (CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC) with an interlaced catalytic surface (ICS) and an open, corncob-like structure is

proposed as an oxygen electrode. Unlike conventional oxide electrodes with a “single adsorption catalytic mechanism”, the ICS of the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ electrode offers a compelling “competitive adsorption catalytic mechanism”. This is attributed to the diverse selective sites within the ICS, where oxygen sites preferentially facilitate oxygen conversion due to their higher affinity for oxygen, while fluorine sites preferentially contribute to the growth of Li_2O_2 owing to their stronger affinity for LiO_2 . This transformation in the formation mechanism of Li_2O_2 and its morphology from film along the electrode surface to toroidal particles effectively mitigates the issue of buried active sites. Additionally, the unique structure of the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ electrode aids in the storage and decomposition of Li_2O_2 products. Its corncob-like open architecture not only promotes the capture and release of oxygen but also facilitates the formation of well-contacted Li_2O_2 /electrode interfaces, akin to a “corn on the cob” design. Consequently, the $\text{Li}-\text{O}_2$ battery employing the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode demonstrates a high specific capacity of up to 30923 mAh g^{-1} and a lifespan exceeding 580 cycles, surpassing most reported metal oxide-based cathodes. This work offers a promising solution to the issues of buried active sites and storage of insoluble products in metal-air batteries.

1. Introduction

The pursuit of rechargeable secondary batteries with high energy density, superior safety, and long-term sustainability remains a prominent goal in the field of new energy and electrochemical storage devices^[1]. Within the array of energy storage systems, lithium-oxygen ($\text{Li}-\text{O}_2$) batteries stand out for their notably high theoretical energy density, reaching approximately 3500 Wh Kg^{-1} . This characteristic positions them as key contenders among the emerging next-generation secondary batteries poised to lead the market^[2]. Nevertheless, $\text{Li}-\text{O}_2$ batteries face several critical obstacles, including sluggish oxygen redox kinetics, strong reactivity of reaction intermediates, undesirable parasitic reactions, and an inadequate three-phase contact interface (electrolyte/ O_2 /cathode), all of which significantly impede their

advancement and widespread application^[3]. These impediments result in substantial overpotentials and shorter cycle lives for Li–O₂ batteries, demanding resolution before their practical realization.

The operation of nonaqueous Li–O₂ batteries primarily rely on the reversible generation and decomposition of Li₂O₂^[3a,3b,4]. Although the basic principle of the Li–O₂ batteries is easy to understand, the actual microscopic reaction elementary steps, especially the reaction process on the cathode side, are very complex. This complexity arises due to multiple interfaces, diverse transformation pathways, and a spectrum of reaction intermediates (e.g., O₂⁻, LiO₂, O₂¹)^[5]. During the discharge process (O₂ reduction reaction, ORR), the initial step involves the reduction of O₂ to O₂⁻, followed by its combination with lithium ions to form the intermediate LiO₂ (O₂ + e⁻ + Li⁺ → LiO₂)^[6]. Subsequently, if LiO₂ becomes adsorbed onto the electrode surface (LiO₂^{*}), the second electrochemical reduction reaction swiftly generates film-like Li₂O₂ along the electrode surface (LiO₂^{*} + e⁻ + Li⁺ → Li₂O₂), a phenomenon known as the “surface mechanism”^[7]. However, if LiO₂ dissolves in the electrolyte (LiO_{2(sol)}), a disproportionation reaction will happen, which leads to the formation of toroidal Li₂O₂ particles (2LiO_{2(sol)} → Li₂O₂ + O₂), termed the “solution mechanism”^[8]. The distinct morphologies of Li₂O₂ generated through varying growth mechanisms significantly impact the performance of Li–O₂ batteries^[9]. For instance, a thin-film structure of Li₂O₂ tends to decompose readily, enabling low overpotentials; however, it also causes electrode passivation, consequently leading to low capacity. In contrast, toroidal-shaped Li₂O₂ does not easily passivate the electrode surface, allowing for a high specific capacity. Nevertheless, due to its lower tendency for decomposition, it typically exhibits higher overpotentials. During the charging process (O₂ evolution reaction, OER), the solid Li₂O₂ product typically decomposes through a direct two-electron reaction (Li₂O₂ → O₂ + 2e⁻ + 2Li⁺). Some studies also demonstrated an alternative pathway involving the formation of LiO₂ as an intermediate during decomposition (Li₂O₂ → LiO₂ + e⁻ + Li⁺, LiO₂ → O₂ + e⁻ + Li⁺ or 2LiO₂ → Li₂O₂ + O₂), which features a comparatively lower charging

overpotential^[10]. Nonetheless, the kinetics of OER remain significantly restricted due to the challenge in electron transfer between the insulative Li_2O_2 and the cathode surface. Therefore, finding ways to promote the efficient decomposition of Li_2O_2 so that substantially reducing the charging overpotential of Li-O_2 batteries remains a big challenge.

Because of the decisive role of oxygen cathode in the formation and decomposition of Li_2O_2 products, the design and development of oxygen cathode catalysts have emerged as the pivotal concern and primary research focus in the realm of Li-O_2 batteries. The structural and catalytic factors of the oxygen cathode hold sway over the electrochemical performance of Li-O_2 batteries, necessitating multifunctional criteria. These include: (1) ensuring an abundance of reactive sites and fostering suitable oxygen species (e.g., O_2 , LiO_2) affinity to facilitate efficient Li_2O_2 formation/decomposition at tri-phase contact interfaces (electrolyte/ O_2 /cathode) during the discharge/charge process; (2) providing an intrinsically appropriate structures to expedite lithium ion and O_2 transportation, as well as the storage of Li_2O_2 product; and (3) ensuring its stability towards reactants, intermediates, products, and electrolytes. Over the last few decades, various materials, such as carbon, noble metals, non-noble metals, and their composite materials, have been extensively employed as efficient solid oxygen cathode in Li-O_2 batteries^[11]. Some possess well-designed architectures enhancing the storage of insoluble Li_2O_2 to improve discharge capacity, while others exhibit substantial catalytic activity to mitigate the significant overpotential of Li-O_2 batteries^[12]. However, few studies have comprehensively addressed both structural and catalytic factors. Furthermore, despite significant advancements in surface catalysis, understanding the controlled adsorption/desorption properties of reactive oxygen species (O_2/LiO_2) and the mechanisms by which solid oxygen cathode regulate the growth pathway of Li_2O_2 products remains insufficient and necessitates further studies. On one hand, enhancing the cathode's oxygen species affinity can induce the growth of Li_2O_2 conformal thin-film on the electrode surface, significantly advancing the kinetics of Li_2O_2 formation/decomposition. Conversely, diminishing the cathode's oxygen species affinity or

introducing soluble additives to encourage nucleation and growth of Li_2O_2 in the electrolyte can markedly augment battery capacity and alleviate electrode passivation. Thus, how to optimize the growth mechanism of solid-phase products and resolve their reversible storage and decomposition issues is a top priority for the development of Li-O_2 batteries.

Here, by integrating catalytic and structural design concepts, we propose the utilization of a fluorine-doped bimetallic cobalt-nickel oxide ($\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$) featuring an interlaced catalytic surface (ICS) and an open corncob-like structure as an oxygen cathode (**Figure 1**). Specifically, the introduction of fluorine aimed to create an ICS with distinctive selective sites on the bimetallic cobalt-nickel oxide electrode. Within this design, the oxygen sites exhibited a stronger attraction to oxygen, while the fluorine sites possessed a higher affinity for LiO_2 . During the discharge process, O_2 preferentially adsorbed on the oxygen site, initiating the first reduction reaction on the electrode surface, leading to the production of LiO_2 . Subsequently, LiO_2 was transferred to the surrounding fluorine site, where disproportionation occurred, resulting in the generation of Li_2O_2 products. This “competitive adsorption catalytic mechanism” significantly altered the morphology of Li_2O_2 , transforming it from a thin film growing along the electrode surface to toroidal particles, thereby notably mitigating the electrode surface passivation (i.e., active site burial) issue. Furthermore, the open corncob-like structure of the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode not only provided abundant space for Li_2O_2 storage but also facilitated the formation of a well-contacted $\text{Li}_2\text{O}_2/\text{cathode}$ interface (“corn on the cob” structure) and the rapid oxygen capture and release. As a result, the Li-O_2 battery featuring the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode exhibited outstanding electrochemical performance, including low charging overpotential, high discharge capacity ($\approx 30923 \text{ mAh g}^{-1}$), and an extended cycle life (>580 cycles).

2. Results and Discussion

Given carbon's excellent conductivity and efficacy as an ORR catalyst, carbon cloth (CC), consisting of numerous carbon fiber rods, was chosen as the conductive substrate for the cathode (Figure S1a-c, Supporting Information). **Figure 2a** illustrates the fabrication process of the corn-cob-like open-structured $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ electrodes grown on the CC current collector through a straightforward two-step synthesis method: (1) hydrothermal synthesis of corn-cob-like precursor nanorods on CC (micromorphology of the precursor is shown in Figure S1d-f, Supporting Information), and (2) high-temperature calcination of the prepared precursor in the presence of fluorine sources to produce $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ electrodes. Altering the calcination conditions resulted in obtaining the counterpart CoNiO_2/CC electrode grown on the CC current collector. This self-supporting, binder-free electrode generated *via* the *in-situ* growth method can be directly utilized as the oxygen cathode for $\text{Li}-\text{O}_2$ batteries without the use of binder, which helps avoid binder-related side reactions and capacity degradation.

Various characterization techniques were employed to ascertain the elemental composition and structure of the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ and CoNiO_2/CC electrodes. The morphologies and microstructures of both cathodes were investigated using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) techniques. Figure 2b, 2c, 2e, and Figure S2 (Supporting Information) illustrate that the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode exhibits a 3D corn-cob-like open-structured architecture composed of petal-shaped slices anchored on 1D nanorods. This transformation of the smooth surface of the carbon fiber rod into a 3D porous corn-cob-like structure facilitates increased storage space and broader tri-phase contact interfaces (electrolyte/ O_2 /cathode), enabling swift lithium ion and O_2 transportation, along with accommodating Li_2O_2 solid-phase products. The presence of uniformly distributed fluorine in the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode is visually confirmed in Figure 2d. The Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) specific surface area of the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode is approximately $74.8 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$,

significantly surpassing that of the CC substrate (Figure S3 and Table S1). The Barret-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) pore size distribution reveals an abundance of micropores and some mesoporous structures in the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ electrode (Figure S3 and Table S1). SEM and TEM analyses, combined with BET results, confirm the presence of abundant microporous and macroporous structures in the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ electrode, with the latter facilitating mass transfer. Furthermore, contact angle tests (Figure S4) demonstrate superior electrolyte wettability of the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ electrode compared to CC, primarily due to its rich macroporous structure. Furthermore, high-resolution TEM (HRTEM) analysis of the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode (Figure 2f) reveals distinct crystalline and amorphous regions. The crystalline region displays lattice fringes with a 0.21 nm spacing in the radial direction, corresponding to the (200) plane of CoNiO_2 , while the amorphous region suggests the introduction of F, transforming partial CoNiO_2 into an amorphous state^[13]. Selected area electron diffraction (SAED) patterns (Figure 2g) confirm electron diffraction spots attributed to CoNiO_2 species (related to (220), (200), and (111) peaks) according to the previous literatures, yet spots related to fluoride are absent, reinforcing the presence of an amorphous region due to the introduction of F^[13]. It's noteworthy that the CoNiO_2/CC cathode, used as a comparison sample, demonstrates a similar corn-cob-like open-structured architecture in the SEM images (Figure S5-7, Supporting Information). The primary distinction between CoNiO_2/CC and $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathodes lies in the absence or presence of F, respectively.

To verify the successful fabrication of the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ electrode, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analysis was conducted to detect the surface chemical compositions of the CoNiO_2/CC and $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ samples. The survey spectrum of both samples (CoNiO_2 and $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x$) exhibited distinct peaks corresponding to Ni 2p, Co 2p, O 1s, and F 1s, respectively (**Figure 3**). The addition of fluorine resulted in a new distinct F 1s peak (~685.1 eV) in the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x$ spectra, indicating a notable presence of fluorine ions, aligning with previous reports^[14]. For the CoNiO_2 sample, the Ni 2p peaks could be deconvoluted into five

peaks. The major peaks of Ni 2p_{3/2} (~853.9 eV) and Ni 2p_{1/2} (~872.5 eV), along with their respective satellites (~861.1 eV and ~879.3 eV), were consistent with prior findings on Ni²⁺ in nickel oxide^[15]. Additionally, a shoulder peak (~855.5 eV) might originate from the surface Ni²⁺. In the CoNiO_{2-x}F_x sample, the Ni 2p peaks' overall structure remains unchanged. However, a new peak centered at ~857.4 eV, attributed to NiF_n, emerges^[15b]. Due to fluorine's stronger electronegativity, this leads to a shift towards higher binding energy in the other Ni 2p peaks. Furthermore, a novel shoulder peak, associated with Co²⁺, appears at ~782.9 eV, a characteristic often observed in CoF₂-related materials^[16]. The binding energy of other Co 2p peaks similarly shifts to a higher field, indicating the influence of fluorine's electronegativity on cobalt ions. The O 1s spectrum of the CoNiO₂ sample exhibits three peaks at 529.3, 531.0, and 532.5 eV, corresponding to metal-oxide bonding, defects or contaminants, and hydroxide, respectively^[17]. However, in the CoNiO_{2-x}F_x sample, the O 1s spectrum only reveals two peaks at 530.3 and 532.2 eV, potentially influenced by the introduction of highly electronegative F. The obtained outcomes affirm the successful introduction of fluorine (F) into the CoNiO_{2-x}F_x cathode, leading to the coexistence of amorphous and crystalline domains at O-sites and F-sites. X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns in Figure 3e depict the CoNiO₂/CC and CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC cathodes, revealing two distinct diffraction peaks at $2\theta = 36.8^\circ$ and 42.8° , consistent with CoNiO₂ crystalline data (PDF# 10-0188)^[13]. Remarkably, the CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC cathode exhibits the same diffraction peaks, indicating no appearance of new peaks related to F introduction, aligning with the previous SADE image results. Furthermore, elemental analysis of both cathodes (Figure 3f and Figure S8, Supporting Information) reveals the CoNiO₂ material contains Co, Ni, and O, maintaining a consistent atomic ratio of 1:1:2, aligning with the CoNiO₂ molecular formula. However, due to F introduction, part of the O sites is replaced, altering the element content proportion of CoNiO_{2-x}F_x, with F contributing to approximately 26% of the atomic content.

Further, the electrochemical properties of the corn-cob-like open-structured CoNiO_2/CC and $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathodes were explored in a practical Li-O_2 battery environment. As depicted in Figure S9 and Figure S10 (Supporting Information), cyclic voltammetry (CV) was employed to study the O_2 redox reactions in Li-O_2 batteries. In the ORR region, both the Li-O_2 batteries with CoNiO_2/CC and $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathodes exhibit a cathodic peak at approximately 2.6 V, indicating Li_2O_2 formation. However, the peak current of the Li-O_2 battery utilizing the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode surpasses that of the CoNiO_2/CC cathode by more than two-fold. This implies a significantly higher amount of Li_2O_2 (i.e., discharge capacity) will be attained for the Li-O_2 battery equipped with the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode during discharge. Moreover, notably, the Li-O_2 battery using the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode demonstrates a more positive onset potential for ORR and a more negative onset potential for OER compared to the one employing the CoNiO_2/CC cathode (Figure S9), illustrating a remarkable enhancement in O_2 redox kinetics for the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode.

To further substantiate the benefits of the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode, as anticipated from the CV studies, a series of galvanostatic discharge and charge measurements were conducted. In **Figure 4a**, voltage profiles of Li-O_2 batteries employing CoNiO_2/CC and $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathodes at a current density of 100 mA g^{-1} with a cutoff capacity of 1000 mAh g^{-1} are depicted. It is evident that the Li-O_2 battery utilizing the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode exhibits significantly lower overpotential compared to the Li-O_2 battery with the CoNiO_2/CC cathode, indicating superior catalytic activity of the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode during the discharge and charge processes. Notably, the marked elevation of the discharge platform from 2.77 V to 2.85 V signifies a substantial promotion in the Li_2O_2 formation process in the Li-O_2 battery equipped with the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode. Figure 4b illustrates deep discharge-charge curves of Li-O_2 batteries with CoNiO_2/CC and $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathodes at a current density of 100 mA g^{-1} . The Li-O_2 battery incorporating the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x$ cathode demonstrates an exceptionally high

discharge capacity of $\sim 30923 \text{ mAh g}^{-1}$, more than twice that of the Li–O₂ battery with the CoNiO₂/CC cathode ($\sim 13039 \text{ mAh g}^{-1}$).

To ascertain the primary source of capacity, the Li–O₂ battery equipped with the CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC cathode underwent testing under an Ar atmosphere. As depicted in Figure S11 (Supporting Information), at a current density of 100 mA g^{-1} , the battery's capacity recorded a meager 2.5 mAh g^{-1} , indicating a negligible contribution. This result confirms that the majority of the capacity in the Li–O₂ battery employing the CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC cathode was indeed derived from O₂ conversions. To evaluate whether the CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC cathode has a more pronounced effect on the cycling stability of Li–O₂ batteries compared to the CoNiO₂/CC cathode, rigorous tests under high-capacity and high-rate conditions were conducted (Figure 4c). Specifically, Figure 4d and Figure S10 (Supporting Information) display the cycling performance of the two kinds of Li–O₂ battery systems at a current density of 500 mA g^{-1} with a cutoff capacity of 500 mAh g^{-1} . The results reveal that the Li–O₂ battery equipped with the CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC cathode demonstrated stable operation for approximately 580 cycles, while the Li–O₂ battery utilizing the CoNiO₂/CC cathode exhibited early failure, lasting only 215 cycles. Moreover, as illustrated in Figure S13 (Supporting Information), the Li–O₂ battery featuring the CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC cathode exhibited stability over 155 cycles, surpassing twice the endurance of the Li–O₂ battery employing the CoNiO₂/CC cathode (~ 69 cycles) at a current density of 1000 mA g^{-1} , with a high cutoff capacity of 1000 mAh g^{-1} . Even at a current density of 2000 mA g^{-1} , the Li–O₂ battery with the CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC cathode sustained stable operation for over 100 cycles, while the Li–O₂ battery using the CoNiO₂/CC cathode failed within 10 cycles (Figure S14, Supporting Information).

Furthermore, as evidenced by the results illustrating cycling stability under high-capacity loading conditions in Figure 4f, 4g and Figure S15 (Supporting Information), the CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC cathode exhibits more apparent advantages compared to the CoNiO₂/CC cathode (~ 47 cycles vs. failure to maintain cycling). This significant disparity in performance within the same

cathode structure may be attributed to the unique and outstanding Li_2O_2 formation and decomposition processes inherent in the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode, thereby enhancing the stability and reversibility of $\text{Li}-\text{O}_2$ batteries. These findings underscore the substantial performance enhancement achievable through the application of the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode, surpassing comparative samples and outperforming most reported metal-oxide-based cathodes (Figure 4e, Figure S16, and Table S2, Supporting Information).

Subsequently, a sequence of characterizations was conducted to analyze the discharge product components and the reversibility of $\text{Li}-\text{O}_2$ batteries employing CoNiO_2/CC and $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathodes. The X-ray diffraction (XRD) pattern of the discharged $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode confirmed the predominant presence of Li_2O_2 as the discharge product, with no observable signals related to by-products (Figure 5a)^[18]. *Ex-situ* X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) characterizations (Figure 5b, 5c and Figure S17, Supporting Information) were performed to ascertain whether the amorphous by-product is present after discharging and charging. The Li 1s XPS spectra revealed that the discharge product solely comprised Li_2O_2 and completely decomposed upon recharging^[19]. Analysis of the C 1s XPS spectra indicated only four peaks (centered around 284.7, 285.4, 286.9, and 290.5 eV) corresponding to C=C-C, C-O-C, C-O, and O-C=O bonds, respectively^[20]. No additional peaks were detected, affirming the high reversibility of $\text{Li}-\text{O}_2$ batteries employing the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode. However, distinct by-products (e.g., Li_2CO_3) were evident in $\text{Li}-\text{O}_2$ batteries using the CoNiO_2/CC cathode after discharge, which is persisting even after recharging. This signifies the poor reversibility of $\text{Li}-\text{O}_2$ batteries equipped with the CoNiO_2 cathode.

The differential electrochemical mass spectrometry (DEMS) technique was utilized to further substantiate the favorable reversibility of $\text{Li}-\text{O}_2$ batteries equipped with the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode. Figure 5d and 5e display the gas consumption/evolution curves during discharge/charge process of the $\text{Li}-\text{O}_2$ batteries with $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode. Notably, these

curves show O_2 consumption/evolution rates proximate to the theoretical value ($e^-/O_2 = 2$) and minimal CO_2 evolution. Additionally, chemical titration was employed for a more intuitive understanding of product formation. As demonstrated in Figure 5f, Figure S18 and Table S3 (Supporting Information), acid-base and iodometric titration results revealed that, under identical test conditions, $Li-O_2$ batteries utilizing the $CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC$ cathode yielded a higher percentage of Li_2O_2 products compared to those with the $CoNiO_2/CC$ cathode (91.5% vs. 71.1% at a discharge capacity of 0.5 mAh). These findings underscore the $CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC$ cathode's effective facilitation of the ORR process and mitigation of side reactions.

To elucidate the generation and decomposition processes of Li_2O_2 , we utilized SEM to examine the surface evolution of both the $CoNiO_2/CC$ and $CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC$ cathodes. **Figure 6** illustrates that during the discharging process, thin-film Li_2O_2 products formed along the $CoNiO_2/CC$ cathode, enveloping the electrode surface. Conversely, a substantial number of toroidal Li_2O_2 particles emerged on the discharged $CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC$ cathode surface, filling the voids in the corncob-like architecture, which is similar to the “corn on the cob” structure in the nature world. These disparate morphologies of discharge products signify that the introduction of fluorine alters the discharge process of $Li-O_2$ batteries. Upon subsequent charging, the discharge products of $Li-O_2$ batteries equipped with the $CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC$ cathode could be completely decomposed (Figure 6c), reinstating the cathode's morphology nearly identical to its initial state. This underscores the excellent reversibility of $Li-O_2$ batteries with the $CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC$ cathode. By contrast, the $Li-O_2$ batteries featuring the $CoNiO_2/CC$ cathode displayed some incompletely decomposed or by-product remnants (Figure 6f), indicating their poor reversibility.

To observe the morphological changes of the $CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC$ cathode during discharge and charging, SEM tests were conducted at various discharge and charging states (0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0 mAh), as shown in Figure S19-20 (Supporting Information). During discharge, small

granular Li_2O_2 particles were generated initially at a capacity of only 0.5 mAh. Subsequently, with increased capacity, both the quantity and size of these particles increased until the entire electrode surface was filled at a capacity of 3.0 mAh. Conversely, during charging, the larger Li_2O_2 particles gradually decomposed until the surface reverted to its original corn-cob-like architecture. These results suggest that, unlike CoNiO_2/CC electrodes that produce film-like Li_2O_2 , the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode significantly promotes the formation of granular Li_2O_2 (Figure 6g), which dramatically mitigates the surface passivation issue of the electrode and enhances the reversibility of the $\text{Li}-\text{O}_2$ battery system. To further demonstrate the excellent reversibility of the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ electrode system, we investigated the surface morphology and product composition of the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ electrodes in the discharged and charged states after long cycling using SEM and XRD. As shown in Figure S21, after the discharge of the 50th cycle, the surface of the electrode still generates a large number of Li_2O_2 toroidal particles, which are stored in the three-dimensional pore structure of the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode. However, after the charging of the 50th cycle, all of these toroidal particles were disappeared, indicating that even after multiple cycles, the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode maintained structural stability and catalytic activity for Li_2O_2 generation, storage, and decomposition. Additionally, the XRD results (Figure S22) revealed that Li_2O_2 remained the primary product of the discharged electrodes throughout multiple cycles, with the Li_2O_2 signal completely vanishing after charging, indicating complete decomposition. These findings suggest that the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ -based $\text{Li}-\text{O}_2$ cell continues to exhibit reversible Li_2O_2 generation and decomposition reactions after numerous cycles.

To gain deeper insights into the physicochemical properties of CoNiO_2/CC and $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathodes and elucidate the promoting effect of the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode on the nucleation and growth of Li_2O_2 products, first-principles calculations were conducted using density functional theory (DFT) (Figure S23 and S24, Supporting Information). Employing a

doping strategy, the CoNiF_4 model was constructed based on the crystalline structure of CoNiO_2 . The calculations revealed that CoNiO_2 demonstrates stronger O_2 adsorption compared to CoNiF_4 , whereas CoNiF_4 exhibits stronger LiO_2 adsorption than CoNiO_2 . This discrepancy indicates that the introduction of F generates interlaced regions (O-site/F-site) with differing affinities for O_2 and LiO_2 intermediates, leading to the creation of an interlaced catalytic surface (ICS). This ICS comprises selectively favorable sites, with one site preferring oxygen conversion and the other facilitating lithium peroxide growth. These computational findings validate that the presence of both O-sites and F-sites enhances the adsorption of O_2 and LiO_2 , respectively. This enhancement promotes the subsequent formation and decomposition of Li_2O_2 , significantly influencing the overall catalytic activity of the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode material.

To corroborate the theoretical findings, experimental investigations were conducted to examine the adsorption properties of O_2 and LiO_2 . The cathode surface's O_2 adsorption capacity was assessed using temperature-programmed desorption of oxygen ($\text{O}_2\text{-TPD}$)^[21]. Both CoNiO_2/CC and $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathodes exhibited two distinct O_2 desorption peaks, attributed to surface oxygen species (~ 170 °C) and lattice oxygen (~ 350 °C). A comparison reveals higher desorption of surface oxygen species for CoNiO_2 than $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x$, indicating stronger O_2 adsorption in CoNiO_2 . On the contrary, $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x$ exhibited lower oxygen adsorption, attributed to the presence of fluorine (Figure S25a, Supporting Information). Additionally, electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) experiments were conducted to validate the cathodes' adsorption capacity for LiO_2 intermediates during discharge (Figure S25b and c, Supporting Information)^[22]. The g factor around 2.007 observed in $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x$ indicates the presence of superoxide, while CoNiO_2 showed negligible signal.

Based on the aforementioned experimental and theoretical results, we have conducted a comparative analysis of the reaction mechanisms occurring on the surfaces of the two electrodes. We propose a novel “competitive adsorption catalytic mechanism” for Li– O_2 batteries utilizing $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode as a catalyst, as illustrated in Figure 1. The CoNiO_2/CC cathode,

comprising solely O-sites on its surface, demonstrates a consistent adsorption energy for oxygen and LiO_2 . Initially, $\text{O}_{2(\text{sol})}$ will attain the first electron from electrode surface, forming O_2^- on the electrode surface, which then combines with the lithium ions to generate LiO_2 . Subsequently, LiO_2 quickly undergoes a second reduction, forming film-like Li_2O_2 products. This process unfolds across the electrode surface, culminating in the formation of a thin-film Li_2O_2 that covers the entire electrode surface, causing electrode passivation. This conventional “single adsorption catalytic mechanism” aligns with numerous previously reported works. In contrast, the reaction process on the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode surface differs due to the coexistence of both O-sites and F-sites. Given the stronger O_2 -affinity of O-sites compared to F-sites, $\text{O}_{2(\text{sol})}$ tends to preferentially adsorb onto the O-site region, initiating the first reduction reaction to form LiO_2 . Subsequently, LiO_2 migrates to the nearby F-site region, characterized by higher LiO_2 -affinity, for the second reaction, yielding toroidal Li_2O_2 products. This dual-site mechanism not only efficiently accumulates LiO_2 , promoting Li_2O_2 generation but also cleans the O-sites’ surface, facilitating continuous active site action. Diverse active species react at distinct active sites on the electrode surface, leading to the dynamic migration of these species during the formation of Li_2O_2 products. This process constitutes a novel “competitive adsorption catalytic mechanism” for the oxygen cathode in $\text{Li}-\text{O}_2$ batteries. Consequently, toroidal Li_2O_2 particles form at the F-sites where LiO_2 accumulates, marking a substantial departure from the behavior observed in pure oxide. Thanks to the “competitive adsorption catalytic mechanism”, the reaction kinetics of $\text{Li}-\text{O}_2$ batteries with $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode is significantly enhanced, thus greatly improving the overall battery performance.

3. Conclusions

In summary, a corncob-shaped $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ oxygen cathode featuring an interlaced catalytic surface (ICS) was successfully fabricated through the amalgamation of catalytic and structural design concepts. The diverse adsorption capacities of oxygen and LiO_2 at the oxygen

and fluorine sites on the ICS surface endowed the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ oxygen cathode with an ingenious “competitive adsorption catalytic mechanism”, which leads to a change in the growth mechanism of Li_2O_2 from the traditional “single adsorption catalytic mechanism” typically observed in conventional metal oxides-based oxygen cathodes. The alteration in the Li_2O_2 formation mechanism transforms its morphology from a thin film growing along the electrode surface to a toroidal-shaped particle, substantially mitigating the electrode surface passivation issue. Additionally, the distinctive corncob-like structure significantly facilitated the oxygen diffusion, uptake and release, as well as the Li_2O_2 storage and decomposition. As a consequence, these inherent advantages endow the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode with notably high discharge specific capacity, low charge overpotential and extended cycle life. This work underscores the pivotal role of catalytic and structural designs in optimizing oxygen electrodes for Li– O_2 batteries, offering novel insights for their future development.

4. Experimental Section

Chemicals and Materials: Cobalt nitrate hexahydrate ($\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and nickel nitrate hexahydrate ($\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) were procured from Sinopharm Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd. 2-Methylimidazole (98%) was acquired from Shanghai Aladdin Biochemical Technology Co., Ltd. Polyterafluoroethylene (5 μm) was obtained from Shanghai Macklin Biochemical Co., Ltd. All chemicals were used directly without further purification. CC was purchased from Shanghai Hesun Electric Co. Ltd. The Li metal foils ($\Phi 15.8 \times 1.0$ mm, $\geq 99.9\%$) utilized in this study were sourced from Shunyou Metal Co., Ltd. (Shanghai, China). 1 M lithium perchlorate (LiClO_4) in DMSO ($\text{H}_2\text{O} < 20$ ppm) was obtained from Fosai New Materials Co., Ltd (Suzhou, China).

Synthesis of $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ and CoNiO_2/CC cathodes: Before the synthesis, the CC current collector was cut into small 10 mm diameter wafers. These were subsequently treated with anhydrous ethanol and deionized water (DI) three times under ultrasonication at room temperature for 6 minutes each to eliminate any potential surface impurities. The synthetic

method was adapted from previous literature. Specifically, a solution consisting of 3 mmol $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 3 mmol $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and 6 mmol 2-methylimidazole dissolved in 15 mL of methyl alcohol was stirred at room temperature. The resulting homogeneous solution was transferred into a 23 mL autoclave, where three 10 mm diameter CC pieces were wetted with methyl alcohol and submerged in the solution at the autoclave's bottom. The autoclave was sealed, and the reaction was conducted at 60 °C for 24 hours in an electric oven. Subsequently, the CC loaded with claybank precursor underwent multiple washes with deionized water and ethanol until no impurities adhered to the CC's surface upon cooling the autoclave to room temperature. The CC with the precursor was then placed in a tube furnace, supported by a stainless-steel mesh on a porcelain boat, with 0.75g of polytetrafluoroethylene placed in the boat. It was heated from room temperature to 600 °C at a rate of 20 °C min^{-1} and held for 3 hours in an argon atmosphere. This process yielded the corn-cob-like open-structured $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode grown on CC current collector. Additionally, the open-structured CoNiO_2/CC cathode grown on CC current collector was synthesized by modifying the calcination conditions without altering other reaction parameters.

Materials characterization: The discharged and charged electrode products were analyzed using X-ray powder diffraction via a Rigaku Ultima IV X-ray diffractometer, employing Cu $\text{K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$) within a scan angle range of 30–60°. Field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM, HITACHI S-4800) was utilized to examine the nanostructures and surface morphologies of both the discharged and charged electrodes. Surface compositions were determined by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) performed on a PHI 5000 Versa Probe II (ULVAC PHI) using a monochromatic Al K (1486.6 eV) X-ray source at 24 W and 16 KV, with a beam spot size of 100 μm . Gas consumption and evolution during the discharge and charge processes was measured using a differential electrochemical mass spectrometry (DEMS, QAS100, Linglu Instruments, Shanghai, China). For electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) measurements, the Li–O₂ battery with CoNiO_2/CC or $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ after discharged for 48

h at a current density of 100 mA g^{-1} was disassembled in a glovebox filled with Ar atmosphere. The corresponding electrode material (i.e., CoNiO_2 or $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x$) was then transferred to a nuclear magnetic tube, which was sealed before exposure to air. Subsequently, the nuclear magnetic tube was immediately transferred to a Dewar bottle filled with liquid nitrogen upon removal from the glovebox. EPR spectra were recorded at -183°C using a Bruker EMX-10/12 spectrometer operating at 9.4 GHz, with a modulation frequency of 100 kHz and a modulation amplitude of 2 G. These measurements were conducted in a quartz finger Dewar filled with liquid nitrogen. The N_2 adsorption/desorption isotherms were tested at 77 K by using a Micromeritics TriStar II3020 surface area and pore analyzer. The surface areas of the oxygen cathode were calculated based on the BET method. The pore size distribution was determined by using the BJH equation.

Electrochemical measurements: The Li– O_2 battery was assembled with an electrolyte-treated Li foil as anode, a glass fiber as separator, 1 M LiClO_4 in dimethyl sulfoxide as electrolyte, and the as prepared cathodes (CoNiO_2/CC and $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$) in an Ar filled glove box ($\text{H}_2\text{O} < 1 \text{ ppm}$, $\text{O}_2 < 1 \text{ ppm}$). The detailed process of the above electrolyte-treated Li foil was mainly based on the methods reported by Bruce et al,^[23] in brief, fresh Li metal foils were soaked with 0.1 M LiClO_4 -propylene carbonate (PC) electrolyte for 3 days and then rinsed with DMSO to remove residual PC before being used as anode for Li– O_2 batteries containing DMSO-based electrolyte. Testing of the cells was conducted in a 1 atm O_2 atmosphere using a NEWARE BTS-5 V/5 mA type battery testing system from Shenzhen Neware Electronic Co. LTD, China. Specific capacity was calculated based on the mass loading of CoNiO_2 or $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x$. The cyclic voltammetry experiment for the coin-cell system was conducted under Ar and O_2 atmospheres using an IVIUM Multichannel Electrochemical Analyzer. A piece of $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x$ cathode was served as the working electrode, while a piece of lithium foil was used as the counter and reference electrode. The voltage window was set at 2.0–4.0 V or 2.0–4.5 V, and the scan rate was 0.05 mV s^{-1} . *In-situ* differential electrochemical mass spectrometry (DEMS)

measurements were performed on a commercial mass spectrometer (MSD, Agilent, 5975C) with EI source. The detailed calculation procedures for DEMS data refer to previous study,^[24] for the theoretical $2e^-/O_2$ line, based on the equation of $Q=It=nzF$, the theoretical amount of O_2 consumed per unit time ($nmol\ s^{-1}$) during discharge or released per unit time ($nmol\ s^{-1}$) during charge can be obtained ($n_{t,d}=n/t=I/zF$). The discharge and charge current we use here are 0.4 mA and 0.1 mA, respectively, and the theoretical electron transfer number (z) is 2 based on the formation or decomposition of Li_2O_2 ($Li^+ + 2e^- + O_2 \leftrightarrow Li_2O_2$). Therefore, the theoretical amount of O_2 consumed per unit time during discharge is about $2.072\ nmol\ s^{-1}$ ($n_{t,d}=n/t=I/zF=0.4/(2\times 96500)\ mmol\ s^{-1}\approx 2.072\ nmol\ s^{-1}$) while the theoretical amount of O_2 released per unit time during charge is about $0.518\ nmol\ s^{-1}$ ($n_{t,c}=n/t=I/zF=0.1/(2\times 96500)\ mmol\ s^{-1}\approx 0.518\ nmol\ s^{-1}$).

Computational Details: To perform our DFT calculations, we utilized the Vienna ab-initio simulation package (VASP) and employed the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) gradient-corrected exchange-correlation functional with the projector augmented plane wave (PAW) method. However, since both $CoNiO_2$ and $CoNiF_4$ are magnetic materials and PBE was unable to accurately account for the d-d interaction of Co and Ni, we adopted the PBE+U approximation with $U-J = 4.0\ eV$ for Co and $U-J = 5.3\ eV$ for Ni. The plane wave kinetic energy cutoff was set to 400 eV. We constructed a (4×3) two-layer slab model for the $CoNiO_2$ (200) facet based on experimental X-ray diffraction (XRD) data. As we were unable to obtain crystal structure data for pure $CoNiF_4$, we built a model for $CoNiF_4$ by doping 50% Co in different positions in the NiF_2 lattice and determined the most stable structure. Subsequently, we constructed a (2×1) two-layer slab model for the $CoNiF_4$ (110) facet. To avoid interactions between periodically repeated images, all slabs were repeated periodically with a $15\ \text{\AA}$ vacuum spacing in the vertical direction. During optimization, both the slab and adsorbates thereon were allowed to fully relax. The adsorption energy (ΔE_{ads}) of LiO_2 or O_2 on substrates is defined as:

$$\Delta E_{ads} = E_{total} - E_{slab} - E_{LiO_2\ or\ O_2}$$

Here, E_{total} , E_{slab} , E_{LiO_2} or E_{O_2} are the total energies of the combined system, the clean substrate and the energy of LiO_2 or O_2 respectively.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Figure 1. Design rationale of our fluorine-doped bimetallic cobalt-nickel oxide oxygen cathode ($CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC$) with an interlaced catalytic surface (ICS) and an open corncob-like structure.

Figure 2. a) Schematic illustration of the synthesis procedure for the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ and CoNiO_2/CC cathode. b-g) Morphology and structure characterization of the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$ cathode: b, c) SEM images with different magnification, d) SEM image and the corresponding EDX maps, e) TEM image, f) HRTEM image and g) SAED pattern image.

Figure 3. a-d) Ni 2p a), Co 2p b), O 1s c) and F 1s d) XPS spectra, e) XRD patterns and f) element contents of the CoNiO₂/CC and CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC cathodes.

Figure 4. a-b) Voltage profiles of the Li–O₂ batteries with CoNiO₂/CC and CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC cathodes at a current density of 100 mA g⁻¹: a) with a cutoff capacity of 1000 mAh g⁻¹; b) deep discharge–charge state. c) Comparison of the cycle lives of the Li–O₂ batteries with the CoNiO₂/CC and CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC cathodes at varying current densities and capacities. d) Cycling stability and the corresponding terminal discharge voltage of the Li–O₂ batteries with the CoNiO₂/CC and CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC cathodes at a current density of 500 mA g⁻¹ with a cutoff capacity of 500 mAh g⁻¹. e) Comparison of the performances of our CoNiO_{2-x}F_x-based Li–O₂ batteries with other solid catalysts-based Li–O₂ batteries. f-g) Cycling performance f) and selected voltage profiles g) of the Li–O₂ batteries with the CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC cathodes at a current density of 500 mA g⁻¹ with a cutoff capacity of 2000 mAh g⁻¹.

Figure 5. a) XRD of the discharged and charged CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC cathodes. b-c) Li 1s b) and C 1s c) XPS spectra of the discharged and charged CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC cathodes. d-e) Galvanostatic discharge (current: 0.4 mA) profile/gas consumption rate d) and galvanostatic charge (current: 0.1 mA) profile/gas evolution rate e) of the Li–O₂ batteries with the CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC cathode. f) Optical photographs of the chemical titration experiments for the discharged CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC cathodes.

Figure 6. a-f) SEM images of the a, b) discharged and c) charged CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC cathodes, and d, e) the discharged and f) charged CoNiO₂/CC cathodes. g) Schematic illustration of the microstructure morphology evolution during discharge and charge processes of the Li–O₂ batteries with CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC and CoNiO₂/CC cathodes.

We meticulously balanced the structural and catalytic factors of the oxygen electrode, culminating in the design of fluorine-doped bimetallic cobalt-nickel oxide ($\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$) featuring an interlaced catalytic surface (ICS) and a corncob-like structure. Benefiting from its unique structural configuration and catalytic mechanism, the designed material significantly enhances the electrochemical performance of Li-O_2 batteries across various aspects. Notably, it demonstrates an impressive discharge capacity of up to $\sim 30923 \text{ mAh g}^{-1}$, an extended cycle life of up to 580 cycles, and diminishes the charging overpotential to approximately 0.54 V. These achievements surpass most of the reported metal oxide and noble metal-based oxygen electrodes.

Keyword: oxygen catalysts, Li_2O_2 storage, Li_2O_2 growth mechanism, catalytic design, structural design

Zongqiang Sun[#], Xiaodong Lin[#], Chutao Wang[#], Yanyan Tan, Wenjie Dou, Ajuan Hu, Jiaqing Cui, Jingmin Fan, Ruming Yuan, Mingsen Zheng* and Quanfeng Dong*

Constructing an Interlaced Catalytic Surface *via* Fluorine-Doped Bimetallic Oxides for Oxygen Electrode Processes in Li-O_2 Batteries

TOC figure

*Supplementary information for***Constructing an Interlaced Catalytic Surface *via* Fluorine-Doped Bimetallic Oxides for Oxygen Electrode Processes in Li–O₂ Batteries**

Zongqiang Sun[#], Xiaodong Lin[#], Chutao Wang[#], Yanyan Tan, Wenjie Dou, Ajuan Hu, Jiaqing Cui, Jingmin Fan, Ruming Yuan, Mingsen Zheng* and Quanfeng Dong*

Z. Sun, X. Lin, C. Wang, Y. Tan, W. Dou, A. Hu, J. Cui, J. Fan, R. Yuan, M. Zheng, Q. Dong

State Key Laboratory of Physical Chemistry of Solid Surfaces, Collaborative Innovation Center of Chemistry for Energy Materials (i-ChEM), Engineering Research Centre of Electrochemical Technologies of Ministry of Education, Department of Chemistry, College of Chemistry and Chemical Engineering, Xiamen University, 361005, Xiamen, China.

X. Lin

Institute of Condensed Matter and Nanosciences, Université Catholique de Louvain, Louvain-la-Neuve B-1348, Belgium.

M. Zheng, Q. Dong

Innovation Laboratory for Sciences and Technologies of Energy Materials of Fujian Province (IKKEM), Xiamen, 361005, China.

Email of the corresponding author: mszheng@xmu.edu.cn; qfdong@xmu.edu.cn

[#]These authors contributed equally to this work.

Figure S1. SEM images of a–c) the pristine carbon and d–f) Co/Ni precursor.

Figure S2. Partial magnified TEM images of CoNiO_{2-x}F_x electrode.

Figure S3. a) Nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms and b) pore size distribution of CoNiO_{2-x}F_x electrode.

Table S1. Results of nitrogen adsorption-desorption for CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC and CC electrode.

Samples	BET Surface Area (m ² /g)	Maximum pore volume (cm ³ /g)	Median pore width (nm)
CoNiO _{2-x} F _x /CC	74.8268	0.035031	0.5536
CC	1.2765	0.000764	0.8496

Figure S4. The contact angles of 1.0 M LiClO₄/DMSO electrolyte on the surface of a) carbon cloth (CC) and b) the CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC electrode.

As shown in Figure S4a, the contact angles of 1.0 M LiClO₄/DMSO electrolyte on the surface of carbon cloth (CC) and the CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC electrode were 44.4° and 22.0°, respectively, where lower contact angles imply better wettability. These findings suggest that CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC electrode exhibits superior electrolyte wettability in comparison to CC, mainly due to their abundant macroporous structure.

Figure S5. a, b) SEM images of CoNiO₂ electrodes.

Figure S6. Element mappings of CoNiO₂/CC electrode (C, Ni, Co, O and F).

Figure S7. a) HRTEM image and b) SAED pattern of CoNiO₂ electrode.

Figure S8. EDS analysis of a) CoNiO₂ and b) CoNiO_{2-x}F_x electrodes.

Figure S9. Cyclic voltammetry of the Li–O₂ batteries with CoNiO₂/CC cathode and with CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC cathode at a scan rate of 0.1 mV s⁻¹.

Figure S10. (a) Cyclic voltammetry of the Li–O₂ batteries with CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC cathode testing at a scan rate of 0.1 mV s⁻¹ under Ar and O₂ atmosphere. (b) Linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) of the Li–O₂ batteries with CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC cathode testing at a scan rate of 0.1 mV s⁻¹ under Ar atmosphere. In comparison to the CV curves recorded under O₂ atmosphere, the Li–O₂ cell with CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC cathode exhibits no obvious redox reaction characteristics under Ar atmosphere, aligning with the discharge curves (Figure S11) observed under Ar atmosphere. Moreover, as illustrated in Figure S10b, the Li–O₂ cell with CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC cathode exhibited exceptional stability within the voltage range of 2.0–4.5 V, with no discernible redox reaction characteristics, aligning with the CV results (Figure S10a) observed under Ar atmosphere.

Figure S11. Deep discharge curves of the Li–O₂ batteries with CoNiO_{2-x}F_x electrode under a cutoff voltage of 2.0 V at a current density of 100 mA g⁻¹ under Ar atmosphere.

Figure S12. Selected discharge-charge curves of the Li–O₂ batteries with a) CoNiO₂ and b) CoNiO_{2-x}F_x cathode under a cutoff capacity of 500 mAh g⁻¹ at a current density of 500 mA g⁻¹.

1.

Figure S13. Selected discharge/charge curves of the Li–O₂ batteries with a) CoNiO₂ and b) CoNiO_{2-x}F_x under a cutoff capacity of 1000 mAh g⁻¹ at a current density of 1000 mA g⁻¹ respectively. c) Cycling stability and the terminal discharge voltage of the Li–O₂ batteries with CoNiO₂ and CoNiO_{2-x}F_x under a cutoff capacity of 1000 mAh g⁻¹ at a current density of 1000 mA g⁻¹.

Figure S14. Selected discharge/charge curves of the Li–O₂ batteries with a) CoNiO₂ and b) CoNiO_{2-x}F_x under a cutoff capacity of 1000 mAh g⁻¹ at a current density of 2000 mA g⁻¹ respectively. c) Cycling stability and the terminal discharge voltage of the Li–O₂ batteries with CoNiO₂ and CoNiO_{2-x}F_x under a cutoff capacity of 1000 mAh g⁻¹ at a current density of 2000 mA g⁻¹.

Figure S15. Cycling performance a) and selected voltage profiles b) of the Li-O₂ batteries with the CoNiO₂ cathodes at a current density of 500 mA g⁻¹ with a cutoff capacity of 2000 mAh g⁻¹.

Table S2. Performance comparison of our CoNiO_{2-x}F_x-based Li–O₂ batteries with other solid catalysts-based Li–O₂ batteries.

Cathode	Electrolyte	Cycle number (current density (mA g ⁻¹) /fixed capacity mAh g ⁻¹)	Full capacity/current (mAh g ⁻¹ /mA g ⁻¹)	Ref.
CoNiO _{2-x} F _x	LiClO ₄ /DMSO	580 (500/500)	30923/100	This work
6Ag-SnSe ₂	LiNO ₃ /DMSO	245 (500/600)	16871/100	<i>Adv. Energy Mater.</i> 2022 , <i>12</i> , 2200791
MoO ₂ -supported Mo ₃ P@Mo	LiTFSI/TEGDME	500 (500/500)	4720/500	<i>Adv. Funct. Mater.</i> 2022 , <i>32</i> , 2209876
NiCo ₂ O ₄ @CeO ₂	LiTFSI/TEGDME	400 (500/500)	5586/500	<i>Adv. Sci.</i> 2022 , <i>9</i> , 2200523
Ru/Co@CoN _x -C	LiTFSI/TEGDME	205 (300/1000)	22043/100	<i>Small</i> 2022 , <i>18</i> , 2204836
PtAu	LiCF ₃ SO ₃ /TEGDME	220 (500/1000)	5049/100	<i>Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.</i> 2022 , <i>134</i> , e202201416
PtRu	LiCF ₃ SO ₃ /TEGDME	120 (500/1000)	3689/100	<i>Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.</i> 2022 , <i>134</i> , e202201416
SnSe	LiNO ₃ /DMSO	380 (500/600)	20783/100	<i>Adv. Energy Mater.</i> 2022 , <i>12</i> , 2103910
CCPN-NiCo ₂ S ₄ @rGO	LiTFSI/DMSO	110 (100/1000)	10490/100	<i>ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces</i> 2022 , <i>14</i> , 36753–36762
2P–NiO	LiTFSI/TEGDME	190 (200/1000)	16628/100	<i>J. Mater. Chem. A</i> 2022 , <i>10</i> , 24538–24551
PrO _x -600	LiTFSI/DMSO	49 (100/1000)	16814/100	<i>ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces</i> 2022 , <i>14</i> , 40975–40984
N-TiO ₂ /Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x	LiTFSI/TEGDME	200 (500/500)	15298/100	<i>ACS Nano</i> 2022 , <i>16</i> , 4487–4499

PCS/MnO_{2-x}@CeO₂	LiF ₃ /TEGDME	302 (200/1000)	15322/100	<i>ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces</i> 2022 , <i>14</i> , 22104–22113
MoS₂/CoS₂	LiTFSI/TEGDME	135 (500/500)	10495/100	<i>Small</i> 2022 , <i>18</i> , 2105752
PtIr	LiCF ₃ SO ₃ /TEGDME	180 (100/1000)	8698/100	<i>Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.</i> 2021 , <i>60</i> , 26592–26598
SAsSe-Ti₃C₂	LiTFSI/TEGDME	180 (200/1000)	17254/100	<i>Adv. Funct. Mater.</i> 2021 , <i>29</i> , 2010544
La_{0.7}MnO_{3-δ}	LiTFSI/TEGDME	375 (300/1000)	29286/50	<i>Energy Storage Mater.</i> 2021 , <i>43</i> , 293–304
CoFeCe	LiTFSI/TEGDME	150 (100/1000)	12340/100	<i>Adv. Energy Mater.</i> 2021 , <i>11</i> , 2100110
Co-SAs/N-C	LiTFSI/TEGDME	260 (400/1000)	20105/200	<i>Nat. Commun.</i> 2020 , <i>11</i> , 1576
Au/Cu@FCu	LiTFSI/TEGDME	220 (100/500)	27270/100	<i>ACS Nano</i> 2020 , <i>14</i> , 3281–3289
Ce-Co₃O₄	LiTFSI/TEGDME	500 (100/1000)	8250/500	<i>Chem. Eng. J.</i> 2020 , <i>381</i> , 122678
Pd@Pd₄S-C	LiTFSI/TEGDME	135 (500/500)	8777/100	<i>J. Power Sources</i> 2020 , <i>451</i> , 227738
MoSi₂	LiTFSI/TEGDME	215 (200/1000)	12708/100	<i>J. Mater. Chem. A</i> 2020 , <i>8</i> , 259–267
Co₃O₄-H	LiTFSI/TEGDME	120 (200/500)	5220/200	<i>ACS Catal.</i> 2019 , <i>9</i> , 3773–3782
CuO-CuCo₂O₄	LiClO ₄ /DMSO	~130 (400/1000)	6844/100	<i>RSC Adv.</i> 2019 , <i>9</i> , 16288–16295
NiCo₂S₄@NiO	LiTFSI/TEGDME	300 (200/1000)	10050/200	<i>Adv. Energy Mater.</i> 2019 , <i>9</i> , 1900788
N₂C₀-TiO₂/CFs	LiTFSI/TEGDME	50 (200/500)	5300/100	<i>J. Mater. Chem. A</i> 2019 , <i>7</i> , 23046–23054

Co₃O₄-e-PANI	LiTFSI/TEGDME	226 (300/1000)	32478.3/100	<i>ACS Appl. Energy Mater.</i> 2019 , <i>2</i> , 2939–2947
CNS-RAs/CT	LiTFSI/TEGDME	588 (300/1000)	5438/500	<i>Electrochim. Acta</i> 2019 , <i>301</i> , 69–79
CeO₂/C	LiTFSI/TEGDME	440 (100/600)	13113/100	<i>Adv. Energy Mater.</i> 2019 , <i>9</i> , 1901751
Co₉S₈-PCF	LiClO ₄ /DMSO	105 (100/500)	6875/50	<i>Adv. Energy Mater.</i> 2018 , <i>8</i> , 1800089
g-C₃N₄/α-MnO₂	LiCF ₃ SO ₃ /TEGDME	40 (500/1000)	9180/100	<i>J. Power Sources</i> 2018 , <i>392</i> , 15–22

Figure S16. Comparison of the performances of our $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x$ -based Li-O_2 batteries with other solid catalysts-based Li-O_2 batteries from Table S2.

Solid catalysts corresponding to serial number in Figure S16:

- (1) $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x/\text{CC}$; (2) 6Ag-SnSe_2 ; (3) MoO_2 -supported $\text{Mo}_3\text{P@Mo}$; (4) $\text{NiCo}_2\text{O}_4@\text{CeO}_2$; (5) $\text{Ru/Co@CoN}_x\text{-C}$; (6) PtAu ; (7) PtRu ; (8) SnSe ; (9) $\text{CCPN-NiCo}_2\text{S}_4@\text{rGO}$; (10) 2P-NiO ; (11) $\text{PrO}_x\text{-600}$; (12) $\text{N-TiO}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$; (13) $\text{PCS/MnO}_{2-x}@\text{CeO}_2$; (14) $\text{MoS}_2/\text{CoS}_2$; (15) PtIr ; (16) $\text{SAsSe-Ti}_3\text{C}_2$; (17) $\text{La}_{0.7}\text{MnO}_{3-\delta}$; (18) CoFeCe ; (19) Co-SAs/N-C ; (20) Au/Cu@FCu ; (21) $\text{Ce-Co}_3\text{O}_4$; (22) $\text{Pd@Pd}_4\text{S-C}$; (23) MoSi_2 ; (24) $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4\text{-H}$; (25) $\text{CuO-CuCo}_2\text{O}_4$; (26) $\text{NiCo}_2\text{S}_4@\text{NiO}$; (27) $\text{N,Co-TiO}_2/\text{CFs}$; (28) $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4\text{-e-cPANI}$; (29) CNS-RAs/CT ; (30) CeO_2/C ; (31) $\text{Co}_9\text{S}_8\text{-PCF}$; (32) $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4/\alpha\text{-MnO}_2$.

The sample was taken out of the glove box, and put into a small beaker with 5.0 ml of ultrapure DI-water immediately. The small beaker was shaken with strength for 30s to promote the complete reaction of Li_2O_2 with H_2O (Reaction 1). The whole titration process is carried out in two sequential steps: (1) Acid-Base titration and (2) Iodometric titration . For the acid-base titration, the base was titrated by employing standardized 5 mM HCl solution (0.1 mL of phenolphthalein in isopropanol was added for precise the end-point indicator, Reaction 2). The solution gradually fades from purplish red to colorless and the titration was resumed till the color was totally disappeared.

The iodometric titration was straightly followed with the addition of three reagents into the existed solution in sequence: 1 mL of 2 wt% KI aqueous solution, 1 mL of 3.5 M H_2SO_4 solution and 50 μL of Mo-based catalyst solution (Reaction 3). The Mo-based catalyst solution was prepared by dissolving 0.5 g ammonium molybdate ($(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{MoO}_4$) and 1.5 g of ammonium nitrate (NH_4NO_3) into 5 mL of 30 wt% ammonia aqueous solution, then diluting the solution to 25 mL total using ultrapure DI-water. The resultant solution turned to an orange color due to the formation of I_2 . Then, the I_2 was titrated to a faint pale yellow color using 5 mM $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ aqueous solution (Reaction 4). Finally, 0.5 mL of 1% starch solution was added for precise the end-point detection. The solution rapidly turned to a dark blue color and the titration was resumed till the color was totally disappeared.

Table S3. Results of acid-base titration and iodometric titration. The titration is conducted on CoNiO_2 and $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x$ cathodes (with separator) to quantitatively analyze the amount of both deposited products and soluble products during discharge.

Samples	5 mM HCl Titration		5mM $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ Titration		Li_2O_2 (μmol) (0.5 mAh = 9.33 μmol)	Li_2O_2 Yield
	Volume (ml)	Mole (μmol)	Volume (ml)	Mole (μmol)		
$\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x$	3.60	18.00	3.23	16.15	8.54	91.53%
CoNiO_2	2.75	13.75	2.55	12.75	6.63	71.06%

Figure S19. SEM images of the $\text{CoNiO}_{2-x}\text{F}_x$ electrode extracted from the $\text{Li}-\text{O}_2$ batteries at a, e) 0.5 mAh, b, f) 1.0 mAh, c, g) 2.0 mAh and d, h) 3.0 mAh discharge capacities.

Figure S20. SEM images of the CoNiO_{2-x}F_x electrode extracted from the Li-O₂ batteries at a) 0.5 mAh, b) 1.0 mAh, c) 2.0 mAh and d) 3.0 mAh recharge capacities.

Figure S21. SEM images of the a) discharged and b) charged CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC cathodes after 50 cycles.

Figure S22. XRD patterns of the discharged and charged CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC cathodes after 50 cycles.

Figure S23. Optimized structures of different intermediate adsorbed on (200) plane for CoNiO_2 and (110) plane for CoNiF_4 . a) O_2 and b) LiO_2 on (200) plane for CoNiO_2 ; c) O_2 and b) LiO_2 on (110) plane for CoNiF_4 .

Figure S24. Absorption energy diagrams of CoNiO₂ and CoNiF₄ for adsorption intermediate (O₂*, LiO₂*).

Figure S25. a) O₂-TPD spectra and EPR spectra of b) the discharged CoNiO₂ and CoNiO_{2-x}F_x cathode and c) KO₂ species.

As depicted in Figure S25c, the g-factor value of KO₂ is approximately 2.007, aligning with the signal observed from the discharged CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC electrode. This finding supports our previous assertion that CoNiO_{2-x}F_x/CC exhibits a strong superoxide adsorption capacity.